

Studies on the Reaction of Iron Sulphide with 2-Methylpropan-1-ol in Vapour Phase

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Manuscript received 8 March 1994, revised 27 June 1994, accepted 11 August 1994

Sulphur elimination from synthetic and natural iron sulphide (FeS_2) by reaction with 2-methylpropan-1-ol in vapour phase at 350–500° and 0.1–1.0 atm partial pressure of alcohol, is reported. Sulphur is eliminated mainly as alkyl sulphide and hydrogen sulphide. Kinetic model based on the theory of nucleation with branching and overlapping of nuclei best explains the experimental results. Kinetic parameters for the reaction have also been calculated.

Chemical literature indicates that there are several methods for the recovery of sulphur from metal sulphides¹. However, very little systematic study in the direction of elimination of sulphur from metal sulphides by treating with alcohols is reported². As a part of the overall scheme of elimination of sulphur by the above method, we have already reported the reaction of iron sulphide with butan-1-ol³. We report here the reaction of iron sulphide with 2-methylpropan-1-ol.

Results and Discussion

The effect of various process variables on sulphur elimination was studied separately on synthetic and natural iron sulphide as per details given below.

Sulphur elimination from synthetic iron sulphide : The effect of particle size and flow rate of alcohol on the elimination of sulphur was very little. Elimination of sulphur increased marginally from 31.6 to 35.9% on decreasing the particle size from $-85 + 100$ to $-150 + 200$ B.S.S. at 500°. Increasing the flow rate from 7.2 to 22 $\text{dm}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$ increased sulphur elimination from 32.6 to 36.4%. It was found that as the contact time increased from 0.014 to 0.066 s at 500° for a 30 min run, the sulphur elimination decreased marginally from 37.9 to 35.9%. With particle size $-150 + 200$, partial

pressure of alcohol 1 atm, contact time 0.066 s and reaction period 60 min, the increase in temperature (350 to 500°) resulted in an increase of sulphur elimination by 11%. The extent of sulphur elimination as H_2S was in the small range of 2.5–7.5%, while that as alkyl sulphide and alkyl mercaptan were 22–28% and 0.78–0.3% respectively. Sulphur elimination for a 15 min run at 350 and 500° were 26 and 33.5% respectively. Sulphur elimination and yield of alkyl sulphide respectively were almost double in the range of partial pressure 0.2–1.0 atm for a 60 min run at 500°. For a 60 min run at 500° and contact time 0.066 s, the sulphur elimination was found to be 22.42, 28.64 and 41.61% at partial pressure 0.2, 0.3 and 1.0 atm respectively. The extents of sulphur elimination as H_2S , alkyl sulphide and alkyl mercaptan were in the range 0.12–7.50, 12.42–27.72 and 0.17–0.36 respectively.

Sulphur elimination from natural iron sulphide : The effect of various process variables in the reaction of iron sulphide with 2-methylpropan-1-ol followed the same trends as with the synthetic iron sulphide. Sulphur elimination increased from 22.4 to 24.4% on decreasing the particle size from $-85 + 100$ to $-150 + 200$ B.S.S. at 500°. Sulphur elimination increased marginally from 23.6 to 25.1% on increasing the gas flow rate from 7.2 to 22 $\text{dm}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$. On increasing the contact time from 0.014

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TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE REACTION OF IRON SULPHIDE WITH 2-METHYLPROPEN-1-OL

Sl. no.	Underlying theory	Order	Rate min^{-1}	Activation energy kJ mol^{-1}	Arrhenius frequency factor A	Validity in term of fractional conversion
1.	Nucleation with branching of nuclei	0.023	3.24×10^{-3}	16.34	0.043	0.41
2.	Nucleation with branching and overlapping of nuclei	0.021	2.37×10^{-1}	16.62	0.753	0.41
3.	Activated adsorption	0.381	1.23×10^{-3}	24.12	0.060	0.41

to 0.066 s, sulphur elimination decreased slightly from 26.3 to 24.9%.

The sulphur elimination at temperatures 350, 400, 450 and 500° for a reaction period of 60 min was found to be 19.53, 23.62, 25.71 and 28.45% respectively. The effect of partial pressures of alcohol vapour was studied at 500°. The sulphur elimination at partial pressures of 0.1, 0.2 0.3 and 1.0 atm was found to be 17.62, 18.36, 20.01 and 28.4 respectively.

From the foregoing discussions on the results of the effect of different process variables, the optimum conditions arrived at for the maximum elimination of sulphur were : particle size, -150 + 200 B.S.S.; partial pressure of alcohol, 1 atm; temperature, 500°; contact time, 0.014 s and reaction period, 60 min. Sulphur elimination under the optimum conditions was 42.1% in the case of synthetic iron sulphide and 29.3% in the case of natural iron sulphide.

The kinetics of the reaction were studied with synthetic iron sulphide in order to eliminate the effect of impurities present in natural iron sulphide. This reaction did not show autocatalytic behaviour, which is characterised by the sigmoidal nature of the time conversion curve. The plots of conversion percent vs reaction period (min) at different partial pressures of alcohol and temperatures were found to be linear. These data were then fitted into the following well-established kinetic models on gas-solid interactions, viz. (i) the nucleation theory⁴ where after initiation the nuclei can grow in four ways : normal growth; nucleation with branching of nuclei; $(\log \theta/(1-\theta) = ktp_{\text{ROH}}^m + C)$, random nucleation with branching and overlapping of nuclei;

nucleation with branching and overlapping of nuclei, $(\log \theta/(1-\theta) = k \log t + p_{\text{ROH}}^m + C)$; (ii) the theory of linearly advancing reaction front⁵ and (iii) the theory of activated absorption⁶, $(-\log (1-\theta) = ktp_{\text{ROH}}^m + C)$. In the above equations, θ stands for conversion, t is the time of reaction, p_{ROH} the partial pressure of alcohol, k the rate constant, m the order of the reaction and C a constant.

The theories of nucleation with branching of nuclei, nucleation with branching and overlapping

Fig. 1. Correlation with the theory of nucleation with branching of nuclei.

Fig. 2. Correlation with the theory of nucleation with branching and overlapping of nuclei.

Fig 3 Correlation with the theory of activated adsorption

of nuclei and activated adsorption correlated well with the experimental data and this is shown in Figs. 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The values of k , the specific reaction rate and m the order have been found graphically from the slopes of the above plots using the relation $k' (\text{slope}) = kp_{\text{ROH}}^m$.

Activation energy (E) and Arrhenius factor (A) have been calculated by plotting $\log \theta/(1-\theta)$ vs time, $\log \theta/(1-\theta)$ vs $\log t$ and $-\log(1-\theta)$ vs time at three temperatures using the Arrhenius equation. The kinetic parameters are presented in Table 1. The rate constant based on the nucleation model with branching and overlapping of nuclei is 200 times more than the rate constant based on the activated adsorption theory. Hence this theory which also has a lower activation energy is the most acceptable model.

Experimental

The apparatus for the reaction of iron sulphide with methylpropan-1-ol consisted of an arrangement for feeding the gaseous reactants, a fixed bed flow reactor and an arrangement for condensing and absorbing the gas/vapour. The apparatus, experimental procedure, identification and analysis of products have been described in an earlier publication³. Sulphur was eliminated as alkyl sulphide and hydrogen sulphide with small amount of alkyl mercaptan. The relative proportions of alkyl sulphide and mercaptan were assessed by gas chromatography. Hydrogen sulphide was estimated by chemical methods³. The solid residue consisted of FeS and unreacted FeS₂.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (I.D.S.) is grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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